

Towards a Sensory-Emotive Domain for Digital Industrial Design Tools

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Abstract

This paper explores the desirability of using sensory feedback (e.g. sight, sound, touch, smell, taste) to enhance the three-dimensional (3D) form creation capabilities of digital design tools used by industrial designers. It is contended that sensory information can be used to positively affect designers' emotions during form creation, and that such a 'sensory-emotive' relationship is presently under-exploited in digital design tools. The work is taken from a wider research project to investigate designing and modelling, in which a principal aim is to discover users' needs for digital industrial design tools of the future.

A series of designing-and-modelling experiments are reported, in which different kinds of sensory feedback and interactive experiences associated with three contemporary modelling media (conventional computer-aided design (CAD), workshop-based blue foam, and FreeForm virtual clay modelling system by SensAble Technologies, Inc.) are revealed. The results show clear differences between the modelling media.

The results are combined with the findings of two complementary creative sessions, leading to some practical proposals for constructing a sensory-emotive domain for digital industrial design tools, whilst acknowledging the opportunities and restrictions of state-of-the-art affective computing technology. It is concluded that the presence of a sensory-emotive domain will enrich both designers' form creation experiences (through increased pleasure, intimacy, captivation and engagement) and outsiders' form evaluation experiences (through improved realism, expression and communication).

Keywords: sensory-emotive, designing, digital design tools, CAD, haptics

Introduction

Senses and emotions spanning sight, sound, touch, smell and taste are fundamental components of being human. They motivate action and add meaning and richness to all human experience. We humans have the ability to perceive our personal emotional state and to experience a range of feelings. Our feelings involve sensing of physiological and biochemical changes particular to our human bodies. If senses can be provoked through product design and stimulated then so too can emotions. This relationship is referred to as "sensory-emotive", a term borrowed from the field of marketing (Hill, 2003) and which acknowledges that to serve customers, emotions – and hence senses – must be provoked and understood.

Buchanan (1998) notes that the resources for emotional persuasion are the same for all design arguments, coming from physical contact with objects or from active contemplation of objects before, during, and after use. Much feeling is conveyed in the experience of

movement, whether in the gestures made in using an object or in the shift of visual attention across an object's lines, colours, and patterns. This is what makes the emotive argument of a design so powerful and persuasive: it collapses the distance between the object and the minds of users, leading them to identify with the expressive movement and allowing it to carry them where it will (Buchanan, 1998:103).

Most research in the area of design and emotion is directed at how completed designed products affect end-users' senses and provoke emotional responses (e.g. Desmet, 2003; Hofmeester, Kemp & Blankendaal, 1996). There is, however, another area of design and emotion deserving of attention, which is not to do with completed products but rather with the processes that lead to their creation. Manufactured products communicate sensory information in many ways. However, the digital design tools on which these products are created and developed do not provide the same level of sensory feedback. They fall short of embracing the richness of human senses and skills people have developed through a lifetime of interaction with the material world (Ishii & Ullmer, 1997). The area of concern for this paper is therefore to examine the prospect of providing industrial designers with tools that will affect *them* and provoke responses from *them* as they conceive and develop new product ideas. Consider a report by Picard (2001), which describes how researchers have shown numerous effects of emotion and mood biases on creative problem solving, perception, memory retrieval, learning, and judgment. Providing designers with sensorily rich design tools is potentially a means to increase captivation in a project and to 'get emotional' about the results, in a similar way to a method actor getting into the mindset of a new character.

The last two decades have seen considerable change in the modelling media used by industrial designers, with traditional (non-digital) media being steadily replaced by computer-based (digital) counterparts. Sensory information in the form of 3D visualisation dominates these digital modelling media. The expansion of real-time 3D graphics and spatial audio accelerators has enabled computers to render apparently very realistic 3D objects (Salisbury, 1999). The development of digital modelling tools, encompassing hardware and software, is the concern of human-computer interaction (HCI) groups.

A recent and emerging theme amongst the HCI community, and of direct relevance to the idea of a sensory-emotive domain for digital design tools, is "affective computing" (Brave & Nass, 2003). This specialism refers to HCI in which a device has the ability to detect and

appropriately respond to its user's sensory and emotional states. Detection is possible through a variety of stimuli, including facial expressions, posture, gestures, speech, the force or rhythm of keystrokes and the temperature changes of a hand on a mouse (What Is, 2004). HCI research focuses on vision and sound, with a minority of researches also working on touch (Tan, 2000; Goodbrand, 1998). Smell and taste are underused senses and almost entirely unexplored in HCI. There are good reasons for this: technical difficulties in emitting scent on demand, technical difficulties in delivery, chemical difficulties, and issues in creating accurate and pleasant scents (Kaye, 2004). The sense of smell is well evolved, accurate and valuable as an interface. It can be an excellent sense for drawing attention: users rapidly acclimatise to an ambient scent, but a change in aroma quickly calls attention to itself (Kaye, 2004). Examples of controlled scent release in automated or computerised environments include: scented films (e.g. 'Smell-O-Vision' pictured Elizabeth Taylor in 1960); scented virtual reality (VR) (e.g. fire-fighter training with tight control over scent qualities and quantities, by Deep Immersion Virtual Laboratory); scented computers (e.g. Olfacom, TriSenx); and scented spaces (e.g. the Bow Street Old Whiskey Distillery in Dublin). Supporting research into computerised scent delivery devices is accordingly well developed.

Other motivations for affective computing exist, beyond the 'humanisation' of HCI. These are variously targeted at building robots and synthetic characters that can emulate living beings – especially humans – and which encompass intelligence and emotion (Picard, 2003). Breakthroughs in affective computing have the potential to dramatically enhance digital design tools of the future. However, it is first necessary to examine in what ways digital design tools could benefit from a much increased and sophisticated sensory-emotive domain.

Sensory-emotive interaction with computers

The way designers experience sensory-emotive interaction with computers can be simplified to two strands: the 'system' and the 'digital model' (Figure 1). Designers create a 'digital model' through use of a 'system'.

Figure 1, Two strands to consider in creating a sensory-emotive domain for digital design tools

- **The system.** This strand is concerned with the computer hardware and software that constitutes a digital design tool. It also includes the wider physical environment, real or virtual, in which designing and modelling takes place.
- **The digital model.** This strand is concerned with the specification of the emerging or completed product design within the system.

In some cases, such as immersive VR design tools, as far as users are concerned ‘the system’ becomes almost imperceptible and ‘the digital model’ dominates.

Sensory feedback and form creation

Experiences that are rich in sensations are known to be especially captivating to people, both intellectually and emotionally (Laurel, 1993). To establish a much enhanced sensory-emotive domain for digital design tools, a good starting point would appear to be the goal of enriching the sensory feedback provided by existing tools and to engage multiple senses. With visual information already well established, attention has already turned to integrating haptic (tactile and force feedback) information into digital design tools.

One system that presently stands out because of its relatively wide use and accomplished functionality is the FreeForm[®] Haptic Modelling System from SensAble Technologies Inc., which features the PHANTOM[®] stylus-based desktop haptic device. Research into the implications of FreeForm for product design and new product development (NPD) is now well established (e.g. Campbell *et al.*, 2004; Sener *et al.*, 2003, 2002a, 2002b). Virtual

physical interaction in FreeForm provides an instructive layer of touch sensation to the activities of designing and modelling, creating results that are convincingly real, memorable and emotionally engaging (Salisbury, 1999). Even so, the realism stops short of duplicating the sounds and smells of modelling real clay by hand. Overall, haptic functionality in the context of industrial design allows designers to experience a sensation of touch and physical properties when they interact with virtual objects with lifelike material properties. Haptic devices exert force in response to a user's manoeuvre at a point of collision on a 3D model, enabling a genuinely two-way interaction with virtual objects, where action and perception are brought together (McLundie, 2002).

Haptics technology allows people to 'feel' and 'interact' directly with virtual objects. Touch is said to be the most intimate sense that makes the world tantalising and rich (Bruck, 1998). Of the many types of haptic devices available, not just those limited to product design, hands are the key locations for haptic sensation. Haptic systems can deliver all or some of the following sensations: force feedback (e.g. object solidity, weight, and inertia) and tactile feedback (e.g. object surface geometry and friction). These senses link most closely with the kinaesthetic senses – the brain's awareness of the position and movement of the body by means of nerves within the muscles and joints (RIADM, 2002).

Lack of realistic sensory feedback can be seen as a shortfall of present sketching and drawing functions within CAD. Mouse-driven operations do not replicate the qualitative satisfaction and experience of pen-on-paper sketching. Characteristics of different pens and pencils such as physical size, weight, softness of nib and nib style each contribute to 'feel' and emotional release during sketching activity and, ultimately, to the quality and type of line work produced and form created.

To enhance sensory feedback during sketching, ongoing research has explored the use of hand and body gestures in a number of experimental studies, making use of either desktop CAD systems or VR. Examples include 'Move On' by Hummels (2000) involving designers in a virtual environment, wearing a head-mounted display with two sensors to register body and head movements and two gloves for measuring finger and hand movements and to provide haptic feedback; and 'TACITUS' by Shillito *et al.* (2004) computer supported conceptualisation software, which exploits spatial input, haptic feedback and stereovision.

Designing & modelling experiments

A series of designing and modelling experiments have been conducted for the wider research project on which this paper is based. The experiments were set up to identify strengths and weaknesses of three contemporary modelling media, spanning two digital media (conventional computer-aided design – CAD, and SensAble Technologies' FreeForm system) and one non-digital medium (workshop-based blue foam). Figure 2 gives examples of form creation for each medium. Many different subject matters have been raised by the experiments, but of concern to this work is the sensory feedback and interactive experience associated with each medium.

Figure 2, Examples of form creation with three different modelling media

In brief, the designing and modelling experiments involved the participation of student and practising industrial designers (n=16), and centred around free exploration, within an allotted time, of a typical industrial design brief to design and model a consumer product. Each modelling medium was used in turn by each participant. During the experiments, the participants were interviewed to elicit their reflective 'likes' (=strengths) and 'dislikes' (=weaknesses) of each medium. Then, a set of formal customer needs for future modelling systems, based on these strengths and weaknesses, was created. In addition, observation notes were taken during the experiments with the specific intention of recording the interactions between participants and their modelling media.

The data analysis procedure was adapted from the methodology for identifying a set of ‘customer needs’ as described by Ulrich & Eppinger (1995). The philosophy behind Ulrich & Eppinger’s methodology is “...to create a high-quality information channel that runs directly between customers (users of a product) in the target market and the developers of the product (in this case the author)” (ibid, 34). Furthermore, the philosophy is built on the premise that industrial designers (and design researchers) must interact with customers and seek to understand users’ experiences of products.

Ulrich and Eppinger do not provide a step-by-step procedure to put their methodology into practice, so in response it was necessary for the author to construct a systematic, staged analysis procedure based on Ulrich and Eppinger’s guidelines, which forms the backbone of the analysis. Two key milestones were set for the data analysis. First, the creation of data charts identifying consensus amongst experiment participants on the ‘likes’ and ‘dislikes’ of different modelling media. This first milestone enabled the discussion of relative strengths and weaknesses of BFM, CADM and FFM modelling. Secondly, the creation of a set of customer needs addressing these strengths and weaknesses, in preparation for proposals for future modelling systems. Detailed descriptions of the experiment methodology, protocols and analysis procedures can be found elsewhere (Sener, 2004). Summaries of the main findings from the set of customer needs and observation notes now follow. The results show each medium to hold a qualitatively different interactive experience.

Blue foam modelling (BFM)

BFM is entirely ‘hands-on’, in the sense that physical interaction with the modelling medium, and therefore the emerging modelled design, is unavoidable and immediate. Physical modelling with blue foam involves sensations of touch, sight, smell and sound for both the model and the modelling tools. For example, blue foam has a characteristic smell when sanded too vigorously, it becomes hot and degrades, and its resistance and colour change. Each of these characteristics provides designers with feedback – a kind of conversation – on how to shape the material in real-time. Evaluation of product proposals using BFM appears continuous, with participants constantly eyeing-up and rubbing their fingers over model surfaces to sense roughness, depth, texture and discontinuity of curvatures. BFM effectively allows unlimited model viewpoints, with designers being able to rapidly change model orientation, place it in new physical contexts and view it in a variety of lighting conditions.

FreeForm modelling (FFM)

Some elements of FFM are, to a degree, 'hands-on', within a virtual environment, through use of the PHANToM desktop haptic device. It is possible to sense the presence of surfaces on FreeForm's digital models through the force feedback provided by the PHANToM device, but it is not possible to 'grasp' models or 'feel' friction properties of model surfaces.

Interaction with models is also limited by the functions and layout of the PHANToM device (Figure 3), on two accounts. Firstly, one's fingers manipulate a pen-like stylus and, as such, the realism compared to manipulating workshop tools is obviously very limited. Secondly, the overall movement of the PHANToM device is restricted to single-handed use with six degrees of freedom (6DOF): yaw, pitch, roll, up-down, left-right, front-back. There is also no provision of two-handed haptic feedback, as is the case with BFM, where one hand holds the model and the other holds the tool. Overall, the level of physical interaction observed for FFM was relatively low compared with BFM, but substantially higher than for conventional CADM.

CAD modelling (CADM)

CADM is 'hands-off', in the sense that designers receive no sensory feedback, other than visual, during modelling. In this way, CADM involves indirect modelling of an object. For the majority of cases with CADM, notwithstanding the use of VR, modelling is progressed solely through hand/mouse and hand/keyboard interaction. Mice and keyboards are familiar input devices having simple correct/incorrect operation, limited spatial movement and are easily mastered. CADM is also characterised by very static interaction with the workplace, in contrast to the hand and body gestures of blue foam modelling in a workshop environment.

Figure 3, The PHANTOM[®] Desktop[™] haptic device

Creative sessions

To complement the designing and modelling experiments, two creative sessions aimed at generating new ideas for future modelling systems were organised. These were held with a group of six practising designers. The first session involved brainstorming ideas around the question ‘what attributes are desirable to have in the system?’. Results of the designing and modelling experiments were used as a stimulus. The second session involved working-up the brainstormed ideas in response to the question ‘how should the attributes be combined as a system?’. Many of the proposals were sketched-out on paper and expanded upon during the session reporting.

Practical proposals

In proposing practical ways to create enhanced sensory feedback in digital design tools, it is essential to consider the direction and overall configuration that those tools may take. The results of the designing and modelling experiments, along with the creative sessions, point to very different ways of physically interacting with modelling media, and provide useful clues to two contrasting directions for future modelling systems. The creative practical proposals that follow are extracted from a more comprehensive and illustrated set currently being finalised (Sener, 2004).

The first direction adopts the point of view that the sensory experiences of physically shaping a material (e.g. blue foam, clay) significantly contribute to designers' abilities to create well-thought-through product forms. It is therefore worthwhile and desirable to bring the workshop environment and associated sensory experiences of 'making activity' into the digital domain. This in turn raises a question of how far the realism should be pursued – and whether it is necessary or desirable for the senses of smell and taste to be included. Certainly in the designing and modelling experiments, much praise and positivity – much emotion – was expressed towards the sensory feedback offered by FreeForm. So in relation to 'strand 1: the system' identified earlier, advanced non-invasive hand devices with multi-point haptic feedback (e.g. fingers, thumbs, palms, two-handed) may be usefully developed. These will allow 'grasping' and more complex 'feeling' of digital models, more closely replicating the physical modelling of, for example, blue foam. Integrated systems where haptic devices and product models are co-located (i.e. allowing coordinated hand and eye movements) will provide additional realism. Investigations into the use of multimodal virtual environments by Shillito *et al.* have revealed "... a strong need to mimic the traditional applied artists' workspaces, with co-location of visual and haptic cues a priority" (2001:135). Work is already established in this area, e.g. Reachin Technologies AB (2004). With regard to virtual materials, these need not be limited to only those present in the real world: the manual manipulation of materials with invented properties could result in new and interesting forms and provoke creativity.

The second direction adopts the point of view that digital technologies can, and should, offer interactive and sensory experiences of a style and type far removed from the physical activity of shaping a material. An example would be a deliberately 'hands off' approach: engaging in a spoken conversation with an intelligent computer and 'talking through' the creation of a product form. This could be within either a real or a virtual environment. Objects could be instructed to be formed with real material properties and processing capabilities, and thus visually exhibit to designers associated opportunities and constraints for form creation.

For both directions, opportunities exist to manipulate the broader modelling environment to contribute to a sensory-emotive domain. The creative sessions showed a general desire for designers to work within more dedicated, customisable surroundings enhanced by digital technologies (e.g. digital design rooms, not simply desktop workstations). Colour, images, sounds and smells relevant to a given product design project could be used to set an

immersive theme and mood, in a similar way to desktop themes and wallpaper in Microsoft Windows or Apple Mac OS. Being digital, these themes and moods would be instantly switchable between projects.

Finally, when considering the various users of ‘strand 2: the digital model’, there are good reasons for making sensory feedback in the context of product *simulation* more prevalent and realistic.

- To communicate sensory elements of product proposals to clients, retailers and consumers, which would otherwise be left to the imagination. This is especially applicable for products differentiated by features that play to the senses.
- To more accurately portray virtual prototypes and establish users’ emotional responses.

Sensory feedback and emotional responses may in the future be possible through advanced haptic simulation of product features (e.g. component flexiness, softness, button operations, mechanical movements, weight, temperature, surface texture, surface hardness and surface friction). The widespread adoption of full-size product representations (e.g. by holographic or stereographic projection techniques) will remove the need for the mind to interpret a scale model to its actual size.

Conclusions and future work

It has been said that conventional CAD modelling lacks the “movements, space, and rhythm” that make a rich interactive experience (Øritsland & Buur, 2000). Recent technological advances have led to the creation of hybrid digital modelling media, combining the haptic (force feedback) characteristics present when shaping workshop materials with the functionality of conventional CAD. The advances are an attempt to provide a level of intimacy previously missing in digital design tools, and are based on the premise that designers’ modelling activities can be enhanced through the provision of multi-sensory feedback. Increased understanding of the pleasurable and emotional aspects of form creation, whether as the cooperative activity of designing-and-making or the dual activities of designing-then-making, will be essential to ensuring the relevance and worth of a sensory-emotive domain within digital design tools.

The provision of multi-sensory feedback can in fact be targeted at two groups of people: firstly at designers, in tools for assisting in the creation of product ideas (i.e. for *designing*); and secondly at other project stakeholders including clients, retailers and consumers, in tools for approving or evaluating a product proposal (i.e. for *simulation*). As a tool for *designing*, two valid and contrasting directions have been identified in this paper: firstly, towards improved emulation of the real world (i.e., sensory feedback for increased realism); and secondly, towards new paradigms (i.e., sensory feedback for abstract and artificial interactions). The construction of a sensory-emotive domain for digital industrial design tools will therefore rely on defining (i) the target group and (ii) the conceptual direction.

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